

Appendix

A Experimental Settings

Tables 5 and 6 summarize the hyperparameters used for SOM and VAE across different datasets. In all setups, the SOM unit vectors were initialized using random samples from the input data or latent space of the first class seen during training (i.e. class 0), in line with the CIL setup. We also experimented with other initialization strategies such as uniform random initialization over the fixed range of $[0,1]$, and initialization with the global mean of input data, but these methods consistently underperformed compared to the random sampling method. For each SOM unit, the respective statistics were initialized as follows: the mean vector was set to zero, the variance vector to ones and the covariance matrix to zeroes. We also explored other initialization methods for the statistics such as using diagonal covariance matrices, fixed weight initializations and statistics derived from latent vectors from VAE (when VAE is used). However, these alternatives performed less accurately than the basic initialization of zero mean, unit variance and zero covariance. In all experiments, exponential moving averages were maintained for the mean, variance, and covariance of SOM unit activations. The following hyperparameter settings were explored for the bias correction:

Table 4: Bias-correction hyperparameters with best-performing values and additional settings tested.

Parameter	Symbol	Best value	Other values tested
Mean	β_μ	0.99	0.98, 0.95
Variance / Cov.	$\beta_\sigma, \beta_\Sigma$	0.95	0.91, 0.99, 0.90

To identify the BMUs in the SOMs, Euclidean distance between the input (latent) vector and the SOM unit weights was used. Euclidean distance produced the most accurate results across the datasets. While we experimented with alternative distance metrics including cosine similarity, Manhattan (L1) distance and Mahalanobis distance (4), these methods did not yield any significant improvements in the experiments.

The VAE was trained using the Adam optimizer, which provided consistent reconstruction quality across all datasets. We also evaluated other optimizers such as Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with momentum and Root Mean Square Propagation (RMSprop), but these optimizers resulted in less stable reconstructions and as a result the SOMs replay quality was affected.

In the CLIP-based experiments (Table 7), we used the pretrained CLIP ViT-B/32 model with weights from `openai`. Unless otherwise noted, the encoder was kept frozen to retain the pretrained visual representation, though in some

Algorithm 2 Synthetic Sample Generation using Mean and Covariance (CIFAR-10)

Require: Trained SOM, BMU coordinates (i, j) , number of samples n , regularization constant ϵ

- 1: $\mu \leftarrow \text{SOM.running_mean}[i][j]$
- 2: $\Sigma \leftarrow \text{SOM.running_cov}[i][j]$
- 3: $\Sigma \leftarrow \Sigma + \epsilon I$ // Add diagonal regularization
- 4: Compute eigen-decomposition: $QAQ^T = \Sigma$
- 5: $\Lambda \leftarrow \max(\Lambda, \epsilon)$ // Clamp eigenvalues
- 6: $\Sigma_{\text{pd}} \leftarrow Q \cdot \text{diag}(\Lambda) \cdot Q^T$
- 7: Sample $\tilde{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma_{\text{pd}})$
- 8: **return** n samples $\{\tilde{z}_1, \dots, \tilde{z}_n\}$

experiments, we optionally fine-tuned only the last transformer block to adapt to the continual learning setup. All images (CIFAR-10/100 at 32×32 and TinyImageNet at 64×64) were internally upsampled to 224×224 to match CLIP’s expected resolution. The pooled CLIP embeddings are 512-dimensional, which were then fed into a lightweight transposed-convolutional decoder that reconstructed images at their dataset-native resolution (32×32 for CIFAR-10/100 and 64×64 for TinyImageNet).

Table 5: SOM Hyperparameters for MNIST and Fashion-MNIST

Setting	Value
Datasets	MNIST, Fashion-MNIST
Image Size	28×28
SOM Sizes ($n \times n$)	10, 12, 20, 30, 35
SOM Epochs	10,20,30,50
Sigma	0.95
Neighborhood Function	Gaussian
Distance Metric	Euclidean
SOM Learning Rate	0.5

B Effect of SOM Resolution and VAE Capacity on Incremental Learning

Table 8 reports the accuracy trends for MNIST and Fashion-MNIST under different SOM configurations. We observe that larger SOM resolutions significantly improve performance, with the test accuracy rising with the size of the grid. In MNIST, the precision increases from 87.95% at 10×10 to 95.16% at 35×35 , approaching the performance of the offline i.i.d. upper bound (95.82%). In FashionMNIST, the performance improves from 72.79% to 81.91% under the same grid expansion of the SOM. These results demonstrate the model’s capacity to retain and learn new knowledge using only synthetic replay generated from

Table 6: VAE and SOM Hyperparameters for CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100 and Tiny-ImageNet

Component	Hyperparameter Value
VAE Parameters	
Image Size	$32 \times 32 \times 3$; $64 \times 64 \times 3$ for TinyImagenet
Latent Dim. ($n \times 2 \times 2$)	32, 64, 128
VAE Epochs	200
Batch Size	128, 64
Learning Rate	1×10^{-4} , 1×10^{-5} , 5×10^{-5}
Optimizer	Adam
KL Loss Scale	1.0
Feature Loss Scale	1.0
Norm Type	BatchNorm
Residual Blocks	1 (bottleneck)
Channel Multiplier	32
Block Widths	[1, 2, 4, 8]
SOM Parameters	
SOM Grid Sizes	25, 30, 35, 40
SOM Epochs	150
SOM Learning Rate	0.5, 0.495, 0.45
Sigma	0.95, 0.94, 0.96
Neighbor Function	Gaussian
Distance Metric	Euclidean
Covariance Regularization	$\lambda=1 \times 10^{-4}$;
Replay Samples per BMU	$K=1$ (default; can be increased)

SOM statistics. It should also be noted that the accuracy is achieved without any generative model or memory buffer, relying solely on the internal topology and statistics of the SOM for stable representation learning and replay.

Table 9 presents the results for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 under the one-class-at-a-time method using a VAE (FT global) hybrid model. We investigated both the size of the SOM and the latent dimensionality of the VAE. For CIFAR-10, the best configuration ($32 \times 32 \times 2 \times 2$ latent, 40×40 SOM) achieves an accuracy of 54.16%, even surpassing the performance of standard split-CIFAR-10 (53.01%). This demonstrates the robustness of our method to finer-grained tasks. In the CIFAR-100 stream, our model achieves an accuracy of 12.41% with the same configuration.

We further evaluate on our VAE (FT BMU specific) method (Table 10), where a separate VAE distribution is associated with each BMU. On CIFAR-10, this method achieved a peak accuracy of 46.10%, lower than the shared VAE (FT global) approach. This might suggest that dividing the latent space too finely could hurt the generalization in the BMUs. A similar trend is observed on CIFAR-100, where the best accuracy is 12.15%. Even though VAE (FT BMU

Table 7: CLIP (ViT-B/32) and SOM Hyperparameters for CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and TinyImageNet

Component	Hyperparameter Value
CLIP Encoder / Decoder	
Encoder (model)	CLIP ViT-B/32
Pretrained Weights	openai
Fine-tuning	Frozen (default); optional fine-tuning of last transformer block
Embedding Dim.	512 (pooled embedding)
Input Resolution to CLIP	224×224 (upsampled inside the wrapper)
Decoder Target Size	CIFAR-10/100: 32 × 32 × 3; TinyImageNet: 64 × 64 × 3
Decoder Type	Transposed-conv upsampler (4×4 → target size)
Decoder Base Channels	1024 (XL); attention at 16 ² and 32 ²
Decoder Norm / Activations	GroupNorm(32), SiLU; final tanh (range [-1, 1])
Training / Optimization	
Batch Size	128
Epochs per Class	200 (cosine LR schedule with warmup)
Optimizer	Adam ($\beta_1=0.9$, $\beta_2=0.999$)
Learning Rate	1×10^{-4} , 1×10^{-5} , 5×10^{-5}
LR Schedule	Warmup 500 steps → cosine decay
SOM Parameters	
SOM Grid Size	25,30,35,40
SOM Iterations per Class	150
Learning Rate	0.5, 0.495, 0.45
Sigma (Neighborhood Width)	0.95, 0.94, 0.96
Neighbor Function	Gaussian
Distance Metric	Euclidean
Covariance Regularization	$\lambda=1 \times 10^{-4}$;
Replay Samples per BMU	$K=1$ (default; can be increased)

specific) is more complex, it performs worse than the shared latent distribution model. This suggests that using a single shared representation might be more effective for stable memory replay in high-dimensional data.

We extend our evaluation to TinyImageNet, a very complex benchmark consisting of 200 classes, which we structure into a 10-task stream with 20 classes per task. This setting is considerably more challenging due to both the fine-grained nature of the categories and the larger classification space. The global VAE (FT global) achieves a peak accuracy of 7.14%, higher than the per-BMU variant at 6.45%. These results further confirm the scalability of the shared VAE (FT global) representation, which maintains more stable replay dynamics than its per-BMU counterpart even under highly complex continual learning conditions.

Table 8: Last Accuracy on MNIST and Fashion-MNIST Datasets (10 tasks)

SOM Size	Epochs	Sigma	MNIST	FMNIST
10 × 10	10	0.95	87.95	72.79
10 × 10	50	0.94	87.97	73.83
12 × 12	20	0.95	90.67	76.24
20 × 20	20	0.95	93.01	79.42
30 × 30	30	0.95	94.28	81.08
35 × 35	50	0.95	95.16	81.91

Table 9: SOM+VAE Configuration and Last Accuracy on CIFAR-10 (10 tasks), CIFAR-100 (100 tasks), and TinyImageNet (10 tasks).

Latent Dim	SOM Size	VAE+ SOM Epochs	CIFAR-10	CIFAR-100	TinyImageNet
32 × 2 × 2	30 × 30	200+150	52.32	12.18	6.88
	35 × 35	200+150	54.06	12.20	7.04
	40 × 40	200+150	54.16	12.41	7.14
64 × 2 × 2	25 × 25	200+150	45.18	11.83	6.89
	30 × 30	200+150	46.53	11.88	6.57
	35 × 35	200+150	37.72	11.01	6.44
128 × 2 × 2	25 × 25	200+150	44.21	11.13	6.66
	30 × 30	200+150	41.77	11.10	6.12

Table 10: VAE (FT BMU specific) Configuration and Last Accuracy on CIFAR-10 (10 tasks), CIFAR-100 (100 tasks), and TinyImageNet (10 tasks).

Latent Dim	SOM Size	VAE+ SOM Epochs	CIFAR-10	CIFAR-100	TinyImageNet
32 × 2 × 2	30 × 30	200+150	44.80	11.90	6.11
	35 × 35	200+150	45.60	11.20	6.21
	40 × 40	200+150	46.10	12.15	6.45
64 × 2 × 2	25 × 25	200+150	42.55	10.82	6.32
	30 × 30	200+150	41.88	10.63	6.35
	35 × 35	200+150	43.40	11.18	6.11
128 × 2 × 2	25 × 25	200+150	40.85	11.95	6.21
	30 × 30	200+150	40.10	11.88	5.99

Remarks: We find that larger SOM sizes consistently lead to better performance across datasets (e.g. $35 \times 35 > 30 \times 30 > 25 \times 25$), which aligns with trends observed on all datasets. However, increasing the SOM size also leads to longer training times and higher computational complexity, as the number of BMUs (neurons) grows quadratically. Similarly, increasing the latent dimensionality in the VAE beyond $32 \times 2 \times 2$ does not improve the accuracy; it often degrades it. For example, using $128 \times 2 \times 2$ results in a drop in precision to 38.94% on CIFAR-10. Larger latent spaces are more expensive to train and may introduce sparsity in the SOM map, which might make it harder for the SOM to organize meaningful structures. These results highlight that compact, well-structured latent representations and moderate SOM sizes strike the best balance between performance and efficiency.

Per-BMU overhead. Training a separate decoder per unit adds ~ 12.6 M parameters per BMU (Table 11), which is costly at 40×40 units. In practice, only BMUs receiving the data are updated, but effective sample counts per BMU are low (< 50 for many units), leading to a poor fit.

C Generative Capability of the Proposed Method

Our proposed model can also be used as a generative model, which is capable of synthesizing samples without storing original data. For MNIST and FashionMNIST, as we only use the SOM for training, image samples are generated using Gaussian sampling as described in the paper. After training, each SOM unit stores the specific statistics in the form of mean and variance, and they are used to generate sample images. Figure 2 illustrates some of the samples generated for each class using this method.

For CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, we combine a VAE and the SOM trained on the VAE’s latent space, where, after training, the SOM statistics store the mean, variance, and full covariance matrix of the latent samples. Synthetic latent samples are then generated using eigen-decomposition of the covariance and then decoded using the VAE decoder to reconstruct the images. Figure 3 and 1 illustrate some of the samples generated for each class using this method.

D Class-Level Analysis (Confusion Matrices)

To complement the aggregate accuracy results presented in the main paper, we include full normalized confusion matrices for all datasets under different variants of our method. Each matrix is row-normalized, allowing us to visualize the distribution of predictions per true class and to highlight which classes are most affected by forgetting or confusion over the course of continual learning. For MNIST and Fashion-MNIST (Figure 4), we evaluate the SOM-only variant without auxiliary generative replay. The resulting matrices exhibit strong diagonal dominance, with MNIST showing nearly perfect separation across all classes. FMNIST, while slightly noisier, retains clear diagonals with only minor confusion

Fig. 2: Synthetic samples generated using Gaussian sampling from the trained SOM. Each row corresponds to one class (0–9), and each row contains 10 synthetic samples generated from BMUs labeled with that class.

Fig. 3: Synthetic CIFAR-10 samples generated by sampling latent vectors from a Self-Organizing Map (SOM) trained on VAE latent space. Each latent vector was sampled from the full-covariance Gaussian distribution of a Best Matching Unit (BMU) labeled with the target class. The sampled latents were then decoded into images using VAE. Each row corresponds to one class (0–9).

among semantically similar clothing items (e.g., shirts vs. coats). These results confirm that SOM-only replay is sufficient for simple, low-variance datasets.

On CIFAR-10 (Figure 5), we compare the VAE (FT BMU specific) and the global VAE (FT global) variants. Both maintain clear diagonal structures, but the per-BMU approach exhibits broader off-diagonal activations, especially among visually similar vehicle categories. By contrast, the global variant produces

Fig. 4: Confusion matrices for MNIST (left) and Fashion-MNIST (right) using the SOM-only variant.

slightly better diagonals than the global VAE and fewer cross-class confusions, suggesting that aggregating statistics across the full latent space provides a more stable basis for replay.

For CIFAR-100 (Figure 6), where classes are grouped into 10 superclasses, both the per-BMU and global VAE (FT global) variants preserve diagonal structure but also exhibit leakage into neighboring groups. The per-BMU variant shows more dispersion, while the global variant achieves slightly cleaner diagonals and reduced cross-group mixing, suggesting modest but consistent benefits from pooling statistics at the global level. On TinyImageNet (Figure 7), which is the most challenging benchmark with 200 fine-grained classes, both variants again preserve recognizable diagonals but suffer from substantial leakage across adjacent groups due to strong visual overlap between classes. The global VAE (FT global) provides a slight improvement over the per-BMU variant, reinforcing its relative robustness as dataset complexity increases.

Overall, these confusion matrix visualizations reinforce our main results: SOM-based replay maintains per-class retention across diverse benchmarks, and the global VAE (FT global) as well as the per-BMU variant consistently improve stability and scalability as dataset complexity increases.

E SOM Representations During Continual Learning

Figure 8 visualizes the CIFAR-10 SOM unit vectors after data was fed through the decoders of the VAE and CLIP after the third classes. This highlights a strong feature of this methodology – it is easy to visualize the progress of the algorithm to determine if it is working properly or not, which is beneficial for optimizing hyperparameters or performing early stopping. Appendix E provides a full presentation of SOM unit vector visualizations after each class (or for every 10 classes, in the case of CIFAR-100) for each dataset.

Across datasets, we observe that the SOMs initially form a well-distributed representation of the initial class. After training on the next class, part of the map

Fig. 5: Confusion matrices for CIFAR-10 with VAE (FT global) (left) and VAE (FT BMU specific) (right).

Fig. 6: Confusion matrices for CIFAR-100 with VAE (FT global) (left) and VAE (FT BMU specific) (right).

is overwritten by the new class, while some regions preserve some information from previous classes, which were synthetically generated from the prior SOM iteration. As new tasks are learned, this process continues and representations for prior classes become more compressed in the map; by the time the final class is introduced, the representation is significantly shifted. However, distinct clusters of previously-learned classes remain in various regions for all datasets, showing that our method maintains earlier class representations.

Figures 10 and 11 show a visualization of the unit vectors after each task for the SOMs generated for MNIST and Fashion-MNIST, respectively. Each image in the grid represents the SOM BMU unit vector after observing class 0, 1, and up to class 9 sequentially in the one-class-at-a-time learning setup. The 784 dimension unit vectors are converted back to 28x28 tensors of the original image sizes, and then scaled back to pixel space. Similarly, Figures 12 and 13 show the SOM BMU unit vectors after being decoded back to images by the VAE. CIFAR-10 shows the SOM state after each class, and CIFAR-100 shows the

Fig. 7: Confusion matrices for TinyImageNet with VAE (FT global) (left) and VAE (FT BMU specific) (right).

SOM after every 10 classes. These images show the methodology retains regions for each learned class within the SOM.

F SOM Architecture and Encoder–Decoder Integration

For datasets trained from scratch, we employed the residual VAE in Table 11, which compresses CIFAR images into latent codes of size $32 \times 2 \times 2$, $64 \times 2 \times 2$, or $128 \times 2 \times 2$, reconstructed symmetrically with ResUp blocks (12.6M parameters for the 32-dimensional variant). For pretrained settings, the encoder was replaced with the frozen CLIP ViT-B/32 visual tower, while the decoder (Table 12) upsampled the 512-D embedding through residual and attention blocks to match dataset resolution (32×32 for CIFAR-10/100, 64×64 for TinyImageNet). In the fine-tune setting, only the final transformer block of CLIP was unfrozen. Latent vectors from either encoder were projected onto SOM grids between 20×20 and 40×40 units, with 40×40 providing the best balance of capacity, stability and, computation. Each SOM unit stored running statistics (mean, variance, covariance), which were used to generate replay samples via the respective decoder.

G Analysis of MNIST, Fashion-MNIST, CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 Results

Tables 13–20 report the full per-task accuracy matrices and forgetting statistics for the best performing SOM model from Table 8 and 9 for datasets MNIST, Fashion MNIST and CIFAR10. We evaluated the metrics: forward transfer (FWT), backward transfer (BWT), and forgetting using the standard formulation of (author?) (26). In all datasets, the model achieves perfect performance on the first task and maintains high accuracy on most subsequent tasks despite the absence of an external replay buffer. The structure of the R matrices reveals smooth

Fig. 8: Visualization of decoded SOM unit vectors from the VAE (FT global) (left) and CLIP-SOM (right) models after the third classes on CIFAR-10 for a 25x25 SOM.

degradation along the rows, consistent with mild but controlled catastrophic forgetting. Since the SOM is trained in a single-head class-incremental setting, the model has no prior ability on unseen classes, yielding $R_{t-1,t} \approx 0$ before learning task t . As a result, FWT is consistently negative and equal in magnitude to the per-class baseline accuracy, indicating that no zero-shot transfer occurs across tasks. BWT values for early tasks are slightly negative, reflecting mild forgetting after subsequent updates, while later tasks show near-zero or slightly positive BWT, consistent with the reduced number of interfering updates. Forgetting follows the same trend: early classes exhibit small positive forgetting, whereas the last task exhibits large negative forgetting, as its accuracy improves from zero before training to its final post-training value.

H Memory Footprint

The memory required by the SOM grows only with the number of BMUs (i.e., the SOM grid size) and the latent dimensionality used for its per-unit statistics as seen in Table 21. Each SOM unit stores a running mean and variance, which scale linearly with the latent dimensionality, as well as a symmetric covariance matrix for which only the $d(d+1)/2$ unique entries are retained. As a result, the statistical memory exhibits an overall quadratic $O(d^2)$ dependence on the latent dimensionality. This memory footprint is fixed once the SOM resolution and latent dimensionality are chosen, and remains stable and predictable across tasks, independent of the number of samples observed. When a single global model is used (global VAE-SOM or global CLIP-SOM), the total memory therefore increases linearly with SOM size. In contrast, per-BMU variants replicate a full model for every unit in the map, causing the model component, not the SOM

Table 11: Architecture of the VAE model used for CIFAR-10/100 (input size: $3 \times 32 \times 32$). ResDown and ResUp denote residual blocks with downsampling and upsampling, respectively. All activations are ELU except for the output layer, which uses Tanh. **Notation:** Type = kernel size or layer type, Str. = stride or upsampling scale, Act. = activation function, Skip = presence of skip connection.

Layer	Kernel / Type	Stride / Scale	Act.	Skip	Output Shape	Params
<i>Encoder</i>						
Conv2d (Input)	3×3 / Conv	1	-	No	$32 \times 32 \times 32$	896
ResDown Block 1	3×3 / $\times 2$	$2 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$64 \times 16 \times 16$	46.3K
ResDown Block 2	3×3 / $\times 2$	$2 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$128 \times 8 \times 8$	184.6K
ResDown Block 3	3×3 / $\times 2$	$2 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$256 \times 4 \times 4$	737.9K
ResDown Block 4	3×3 / $\times 2$	$2 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$512 \times 2 \times 2$	2.36M
ResBlock	3×3 / $\times 2$	$1 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$512 \times 2 \times 2$	2.36M
Conv2d (μ)	1×1 / Conv	1	-	No	$32 \times 2 \times 2$	16.4K
Conv2d ($\log\sigma^2$)	1×1 / Conv	1	-	No	$32 \times 2 \times 2$	16.4K
<i>Decoder</i>						
Conv2d (Latent)	1×1 / Conv	1	ELU	No	$512 \times 2 \times 2$	16.9K
ResBlock	3×3 / $\times 2$	$1 + 1$	ELU	Yes	$512 \times 2 \times 2$	2.36M
ResUp Block 1	3×3 / $\times 2$	Upsample $\times 2$	ELU	Yes	$256 \times 4 \times 4$	627.4K
ResUp Block 2	3×3 / $\times 2$	Upsample $\times 2$	ELU	Yes	$128 \times 8 \times 8$	295.2K
ResUp Block 3	3×3 / $\times 2$	Upsample $\times 2$	ELU	Yes	$64 \times 16 \times 16$	184.5K
ResUp Block 4	3×3 / $\times 2$	Upsample $\times 2$	ELU	Yes	$32 \times 32 \times 32$	82.9K
Conv2d (Output)	5×5 / Conv	1	Tanh	No	$3 \times 32 \times 32$	2.4K
Total Parameters						12.6M

component, to grow into hundreds or even thousands of gigabytes for moderate grids (e.g., 40×40) when using modern backbones such as CLIP. This distinction highlights that the SOM itself remains compact and controlled, while the choice of global vs. per-unit generative model determines how the overall system scales with model complexity.

To reduce the memory overhead of per-BMU generative models, we are exploring more parameter-efficient alternatives that avoid duplicating full model backbones for each unit. In particular, we are investigating partial fine-tuning strategies, such as updating only the final transformer block in CLIP or the upper layers of the VAE decoder, while keeping the rest of the network shared and frozen. Importantly, these changes affect only the model component as the SOM itself remains compact, with memory determined solely by the grid size and latent dimensionality. This highlights that the SOM continues to act as a lightweight and scalable structural backbone. Meanwhile, ongoing work is focused on improving the efficiency of models (such as VAE, CLIP) built on top of it.

Table 12: Decoder Architecture used for CLIP+SOM experiments. The encoder is the CLIP ViT-B/32 visual tower (pretrained) and is *frozen* by default; when `finetune_last` is enabled, only the last transformer block of ViT-B/32 is unfrozen. The decoder upsamples a single CLIP embedding to the target RGB image in $[-1, 1]$. **Notation:** Blk = number of blocks, Act. = activation function, GN = GroupNorm(32).

Layer	Op.	Blk	Act.	GN	Output Shape
Linear (embed \rightarrow 4 \times 4)	FC($D\rightarrow$ base_ch \cdot 4 \cdot 4)	–	–	Yes	$B\times 1024\times 4\times 4$
ResBlock	Conv 3 \times 3 (GN+SiLU)	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 1024\times 4\times 4$
Upsample	ConvTranspose2d 4 \times 4	$\times 2$	–	Yes	$B\times 1024\times 8\times 8$
ResBlock (ch \downarrow)	Conv 3 \times 3 (GN+SiLU)	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 512\times 8\times 8$
Upsample	ConvTranspose2d 4 \times 4	$\times 2$	–	Yes	$B\times 512\times 16\times 16$
ResBlock (+Attn)	Conv 3 \times 3 + SelfAttn2d	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 512\times 16\times 16$
ResBlock (ch \downarrow)	Conv 3 \times 3 (GN+SiLU)	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 256\times 16\times 16$
Upsample	ConvTranspose2d 4 \times 4	$\times 2$	–	Yes	$B\times 256\times 32\times 32$
ResBlock (+Attn)	Conv 3 \times 3 + SelfAttn2d	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 256\times 32\times 32$
ResBlock (ch \downarrow)	Conv 3 \times 3 (GN+SiLU)	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 128\times 32\times 32$
Upsample	ConvTranspose2d 4 \times 4	$\times 2$	–	Yes	$B\times 128\times 64\times 64$
ResBlock	Conv 3 \times 3 (GN+SiLU)	1+1	SiLU	Yes	$B\times 128\times Y\times Y$
Output head	GN \rightarrow SiLU \rightarrow 3 \times 3 \rightarrow Tanh	1	Tanh	Yes	$B\times 3\times Y\times Y$

Notes: Encoder output dim $D=512$ for ViT-B/32. SelfAttention2d uses 4 heads with GN(32). By default, only the decoder is trainable; enabling `finetune_last` unfreezes the last ViT block. Decoder output target (Y) size is set to match dataset resolution (32 \times 32 for CIFAR-10/100, 64 \times 64 for TinyImageNet).

I Gaussianity Analysis of Latent Representations and SOM Replay

We examine whether the encoder’s latent representations exhibit systematic deviations from Gaussianity that could undermine the validity of Gaussian replay at the level of individual SOM units using the Shapiro–Wilk (41) test, complemented by visual diagnostics based on quantile–quantile (Q–Q) plots. All experiments in this section are conducted on CIFAR-10, using 5,000 real images and 5,000 generated images along with the 35 \times 35 trained SOM model. Latent codes are extracted from the encoder trained from scratch, without external pretraining. For all statistical tests, latent dimensions are standardized to a zero mean and unit variance prior to analysis.

Q–Q analysis of latent dimensions: Figure 9 (panels a–d) presents Q–Q plots for four representative latent dimensions. These dimensions correspond to individual coordinates of the flattened latent vector and are selected for visualization only where each plot compares empirical quantiles of standardized latent values to those of a standard normal distribution. Across all dimensions tested, the empirical

Table 13: Per-task class accuracy matrix $R[t, j]$ for SOM (35×35) on MNIST (10 tasks, one class at a time).

$t \setminus j$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	1.0000	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
1	0.9997	0.9995	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2	0.9985	0.9978	0.9875	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
3	0.9972	0.9980	0.9836	0.9894	–	–	–	–	–	–
4	0.9960	0.9972	0.9821	0.9866	0.9902	–	–	–	–	–
5	0.9940	0.9975	0.9784	0.9698	0.9852	0.9554	–	–	–	–
6	0.9908	0.9960	0.9752	0.9674	0.9835	0.9496	0.9742	–	–	–
7	0.9894	0.9952	0.9706	0.9648	0.9820	0.9462	0.9738	0.9730	–	–
8	0.9878	0.9940	0.9662	0.9610	0.9786	0.9440	0.9712	0.9704	0.9310	–
9	0.9862	0.9922	0.9618	0.9584	0.9736	0.9406	0.9704	0.9672	0.9282	0.9620

Table 14: Per-task Forward Transfer (FWT), Backward Transfer (BWT), and Forgetting for MNIST for a 35×35 SOM configuration.

Class (Task)	FWT	BWT	Forgetting
0	-0.7133	–	–
1	-0.8943	-0.0073	0.0073
2	-0.4002	-0.0257	0.0257
3	-0.4723	-0.0310	0.0310
4	-0.3595	-0.0166	0.0166
5	-0.3901	-0.0148	0.0148
6	-0.7589	-0.0038	0.0038
7	-0.2977	-0.0058	0.0058
8	-0.3203	-0.0028	0.0028
9	-0.4767	0.0000	–

quantiles closely follow the theoretical diagonal, with only minor deviations observed in the extreme tails, as seen in Figure 9.

Correlation structure of standardized latents: Figure 9 (panel e) visualizes a 20×20 subset of the covariance matrix computed from standardized latent representations. The matrix is strongly diagonally dominant, indicating that most latent dimensions are only weakly correlated. While these correlations are generally small, we retain the full covariance structure during replay to capture any remaining dependencies and to avoid assumptions of independence between latent dimensions.

Shapiro–Wilk test results: Figure 9 (panel f) reports the distribution of Shapiro–Wilk (41) p-values computed independently for 15 latent dimensions using globally pooled samples. While some dimensions fall below the conventional $\alpha = 0.05$ threshold, a substantial fraction do not reject Gaussianity.

Table 15: Per-task class accuracy matrix $R[t, j]$ for SOM (35×35) on Fashion-MNIST (10 tasks, one class at a time).

$t \setminus j$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	1.0000	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
1	0.9962	0.9870	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2	0.9680	0.9804	0.9640	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
3	0.9402	0.9576	0.9504	0.9200	–	–	–	–	–	–
4	0.9496	0.9642	0.7710	0.8554	0.7702	–	–	–	–	–
5	0.9360	0.9618	0.7868	0.8662	0.7344	0.9984	–	–	–	–
6	0.8524	0.9606	0.7324	0.8520	0.7230	0.9978	0.4708	–	–	–
7	0.8726	0.9594	0.7122	0.8550	0.7124	0.9402	0.4580	0.9338	–	–
8	0.8720	0.9586	0.7074	0.8496	0.7090	0.9460	0.4188	0.9312	0.9520	–
9	0.8602	0.9508	0.7100	0.8324	0.6880	0.9318	0.4360	0.8710	0.9390	0.8920

Table 16: Per-task Forward Transfer (FWT), Backward Transfer (BWT), and Forgetting for Fashion-MNIST for a 35×35 SOM configuration.

Class (Task)	FWT	BWT	Forgetting
0	-0.690	–	–
1	-0.6810	-0.0362	0.0362
2	-0.5130	-0.2540	0.2540
3	-0.6860	-0.0876	0.0876
4	-0.4900	-0.0822	0.0822
5	-0.5540	-0.0666	0.0666
6	-0.2680	-0.0348	0.0348
7	-0.4010	-0.0628	0.0628
8	-0.6150	-0.0130	0.0130
9	-0.8130	0.0000	–

The Shapiro–Wilk test is known to be highly sensitive in large-sample regimes, where even mild tail deviations can lead to statistical rejection. Accordingly, these results are interpreted jointly with the Q–Q diagnostics, which consistently indicate approximate normality of marginal latent distributions despite occasional low p-values.

Overall, these findings indicate that the learned latent representations are approximately Gaussian at both the global level and within individual SOM units. This empirical evidence supports the use of per-unit Gaussian modeling for synthetic replay in our continual learning framework.

Table 17: Per-task class accuracy matrix R for CIFAR-10 across 10 sequential tasks for a 40x40 SOM with a global VAE with latent dimension 32x2x2 configuration.

$t \setminus j$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0.863	0.819	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	0.718	0.780	0.768	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	0.680	0.765	0.583	0.610	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	0.653	0.764	0.453	0.558	0.528	-	-	-	-	-
5	0.650	0.762	0.425	0.420	0.512	0.445	-	-	-	-
6	0.648	0.759	0.404	0.355	0.461	0.441	0.569	-	-	-
7	0.637	0.740	0.399	0.350	0.415	0.424	0.559	0.619	-	-
8	0.506	0.723	0.380	0.349	0.410	0.420	0.564	0.616	0.734	-
9	0.580	0.640	0.400	0.260	0.440	0.450	0.570	0.620	0.740	0.720

Table 18: Per-task Forward Transfer (FWT), Backward Transfer (BWT), and Forgetting for all 10 CIFAR-10 tasks for a 40x40 SOM with a global VAE with latent dimension 32x2x2 configuration.

Class (Task)	FWT	BWT	Forgetting
0	-0.323	-	-
1	-0.203	-0.179	0.179
2	-0.161	-0.368	0.368
3	-0.065	-0.350	0.350
4	-0.160	-0.088	0.088
5	-0.192	0.005	-0.005
6	-0.212	0.001	-0.001
7	-0.223	0.001	-0.001
8	-0.329	0.006	-0.006
9	-0.261	0.000	-

Table 19: Task accuracy matrix R for CIFAR-100 across 10 sequential tasks for a 40x40 SOM with a global VAE with latent dimension 32x2x2 configuration.

$t \setminus j$	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0.812	0.603	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	0.402	0.381	0.364	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	0.361	0.372	0.350	0.342	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	0.329	0.345	0.322	0.337	0.310	-	-	-	-	-
5	0.301	0.321	0.298	0.314	0.296	0.284	-	-	-	-
6	0.277	0.298	0.284	0.296	0.281	0.269	0.259	-	-	-
7	0.253	0.276	0.264	0.279	0.268	0.257	0.247	0.236	-	-
8	0.192	0.209	0.204	0.216	0.211	0.203	0.198	0.191	0.187	-
9	0.120	0.120	0.110	0.210	0.110	0.140	0.140	0.140	0.110	0.140

Table 20: Per-task Forward Transfer (FWT), Backward Transfer (BWT), and Forgetting for all 10 CIFAR-100 tasks for a 40x40 SOM with a global VAE with latent dimension 32x2x2 configuration.

Class (Task)	FWT	BWT	Forgetting
0	-0.228	–	–
1	-0.102	-0.483	0.483
2	-0.089	-0.254	0.254
3	-0.082	-0.132	0.132
4	-0.079	-0.200	0.200
5	-0.075	-0.144	0.144
6	-0.073	-0.119	0.119
7	-0.071	-0.096	0.096
8	-0.069	-0.077	0.077
9	-0.067	0.000	-0.140

Fig. 9: **Gaussianity analysis of encoder latent representations on CIFAR-10.** Panels (a–d) show Q–Q plots for four representative standardized latent dimensions, comparing empirical quantiles (y-axis) against a standard normal distribution (x-axis). The close alignment with the diagonal indicates approximate marginal Gaussianity, with only minor deviations in the tails. Panel (e) visualizes a subset of the covariance matrix computed from standardized latents of a 20 x 20 covariance subset, revealing a strong diagonal structure and weak inter-dimensional correlations. Panel (f) shows the distribution of Shapiro–Wilk p-values across tested latent dimensions (red dashed line denotes $\alpha = 0.05$). All results are computed using 5,000 real and 5,000 generated samples.

Table 21: Memory footprint (MB) of SOM-only, VAE-SOM, Per-BMU VAE-SOM, and CLIP-SOM across different SOM sizes and latent dimensions. All values include SOM weights + SOM running statistics (mean, variance, covariance). The replay buffer is not used since each replay is generated at each iteration. VAE parameters are fixed at 12.6M (50.4 MB). CLIP encoder and the decoder trained with CLIP-embeddings contribute 348 MB and 460 MB, respectively; a total of 808 MB per CLIP unit.

Latent (Dim)	SOM Size	SOM Memory (MB)	Extra Model Memory (MB)	Total (MB)
On MNIST and FMNIST (mean-variance method)				
SOM-only				
–	10×10	0.60	–	0.60
–	12×12	0.86	–	0.86
–	20×20	2.39	–	2.39
–	30×30	5.38	–	5.38
–	35×35	7.33	–	7.33
On CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 (full-covariance)				
VAE-SOM (Global VAE, 12.6M params = 50.4 MB)				
32x2x2	25×25	20.31	50.4	70.71
32x2x2	30×30	28.54	50.4	78.94
32x2x2	35×35	38.36	50.4	88.76
32x2x2	40×40	50.74	50.4	101.14
CLIP-SOM (Global CLIP)				
512	25×25	316.69	808	1,124.69
512	30×30	456.03	808	1,264.03
512	35×35	620.70	808	1,428.70
512	40×40	810.72	808	1,618.72
Per-BMU VAE (One VAE per Unit, 50.4 MB each)				
32×2×2	25×25	20.31	31,500	31,520.31
32×2×2	30×30	28.54	45,360	45,388.54
32×2×2	35×35	38.36	61,740	61,778.36
32×2×2	40×40	50.74	80,640	80,690.74
Per-BMU CLIP (CLIP per Unit)				
512	25×25	316.69	505,000	505,316.69
512	30×30	456.03	727,200	727,656.03
512	35×35	620.70	989,800	990,420.70
512	40×40	810.72	1,292,800	1,293,610.72

Fig. 10: Visualization of the SOM unit vectors after each task for MNIST (35×35 SOM).

Fig. 11: Visualization of SOM unit vectors after each task for Fashion-MNIST (35×35 SOM).

Fig. 12: Visualization of decoded SOM unit vectors after each task on CIFAR-10 (40x40 SOM).

Fig. 13: Visualization of decoded SOM unit vectors after every 10 tasks on CIFAR-100 (50x50 SOM).